

Euphresco

Final Report

**Diagnosis of *Xylella fastidiosa*: detection on dormant plants,
important for Mediterranean countries
(Xf-DORM)**

Project duration:

Start date:	2023-01-01
End date:	2025-03-31

Contents

1. Research consortium partners	3
2. Short project report.....	7
2.1. Short executive summary.....	7
2.2. Project aims	7
2.3. Description of the main activities	8
2.4. Main results.....	19
2.5. Conclusions and recommendations to policy makers.....	19
2.6. Benefits from trans-national cooperation.....	19
3. Outreach.....	19
3.1. Article(s) for publication in journals.....	19
3.2. Grey literature	19
3.3. Events	19
4. Open Euphresco data	20
Appendix I Detailed TPS report	20

1. Research consortium partners

Coordinator – Partner 1			
Organisation	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety, Plant health laboratory, France		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Anne-Laure Boutigny, Valérie Olivier, Bruno Legendre	Gender:	F, F, M
Postal Address	7 rue Jean Dixmeras 49044 Angers cedex 01 France		
E-mail	anne-laure.boutigny@anses.fr, valerie.olivier@anses.fr, bruno.legendre@anses.fr		
Phone	+33 2 41 20 74 54		

Partner 2			
Organisation	New South Wales Department of Primary Industry, Australia		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Toni Chapman	Gender:	F
Postal Address	Elizabeth Macarthur Agricultural Institute, Woodbridge Road, Menangle, NSW 2568, Australia		
E-mail	toni.chapman@dpi.nsw.gov.au		
Phone	+61 2 46 40 62 19		

Partner 3			
Organisation	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, Belgium		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Jolien Venneman	Gender:	F
Postal Address	Burg. Van Gansberghelaan 96, 9820 Merelbeke, Belgium		
E-mail	Jolien.Venneman@ilvo.vlaanderen.be		
Phone	+32 9 272 24 31		

Partner 4			
Organisation	Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs, United Kingdom		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Amy Eacock	Gender:	F
Postal Address	Forest Research, Alice Holt Lodge, Wrecclesham, Surrey, GU10 4LH, United Kingdom		
E-mail	amy.eacock@forestresearch.gov.uk		
Phone	+44 (0)300 067 5600		

Partner 5			
Organisation	Fera Science Ltd, United Kingdom		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Jennifer Cole	Gender:	F
Postal Address	York Biotech Campus, Sand Hutton, York, YO41 1LZ, United Kingdom		
E-mail	jennifer.cole@fera.co.uk		
Phone	01904462193		

Partner 6			
Organisation	SASA, United Kingdom		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Alan McCluskey	Gender:	M
Postal Address	Roddinglaw Road, Edinburgh, EH12 9FJ, Scotland		
E-mail	alan.mccluskey@sasa.gov.scot		
Phone	01312448890		

Partner 7			
Organisation	Ministry of Agriculture, Plant Biosecurity, Plant Protection and Inspection Services, Israel		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Yael Meller Harel	Gender:	F
Postal Address	Plant Diseases Diagnostics, Plant Protection and Inspection Services, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, P.O.B 30, BetDagan, 5025001, Israel		
E-mail	yaelm@moag.gov.il		
Phone	+ 97239681534		

Partner 8			
Organisation	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, Ireland		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Thi Thuy Do	Gender:	F
Postal Address	Plant Health Laboratory, Backweston Lab Complex, Young's Cross, Celbridge, Co. Kildare, Ireland, W23 X3PH		
E-mail	thithuy.do@agriculture.gov.ie		
Phone	+353 (0) 1 615 7100		

Partner 9			
Organisation	Council for agronomic research and economic analysis, Italy		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Stefania Loreti	Gender:	F
Postal Address	Via Carlo Giuseppe Bertero 22, 00156 Roma, Italy		
E-mail	stefania.loreti@crea.gov.it		
Phone	+390682070341		

Partner 10			
Organisation	National Council of Research, Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection, Italy		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Giuliana Loconsole	Gender:	F
Postal Address	Via Amendola 122/D, 70126 Bari, Italy		
E-mail	giuliana.loconsole@ipsp.cnr.it		
Phone	+390805443068		

Partner 11			
Organisation	Institute for Agricultural Research, Morocco		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Samir Fakhour	Gender:	M
Postal Address			
E-mail	samir.fakhour@inra.ma		
Phone			

Partner 12			
Organisation	Netherlands Food and Consumer Products Safety Authority, Netherlands		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Chiel Pel	Gender:	M
Postal Address	Postbus 9102, 6700 HC, Wageningen, The Netherlands		
E-mail	m.j.c.pel@nvwa.nl		
Phone	+31(0)625132726		

Partner 13			
Organisation	National Agriculture Research Center, Ministry of Agriculture, Palestine		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Osama Alabdallah	Gender:	M
Postal Address	P.O. Box (209) Qabatya, Jenin, Palestine		
E-mail	oalabdallah@gmail.com		
Phone	00970599741950		

Partner 14			
Organisation	National Institute of Biology (NIB), Slovenia		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Manca Pirc, Tanja Dreo	Gender:	F, F
Postal Address	Vecna pot 111, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia		
E-mail	manca.pirc@nib.si, tanja.dreo@nib.si		
Phone	+38640209820		

Partner 15			
Organisation	Valencian Institute of Agricultural Research, Spain		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Ester Marco Noales	Gender:	F
Postal Address	Carretera CV-315, Km 10,7 46113 - Moncada (Valencia) Spain		
E-mail	marco_est@gva.es		
Phone	+34963424000		

Partner 16			
Organisation	Agdia, Inc., United States of America		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Deborah Groth-Helms	Gender:	F
Postal Address	52642 County Road 1, Elkhart, Indiana, 46514		
E-mail	dgroth@agdia.com		
Phone	574-264-2615		

Partner 17			
Organisation	Ministry of Food Agriculture and Forestry, General Directorate of Food and Control, Turkey		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Nursen Üstün	Gender:	M
Postal Address			
E-mail	nursen.ustun@tarimorman.gov.tr		
Phone			

Partner 18			
Organisation	US Department of Agriculture, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service, United States of America		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Jarred Yasuhara-Bell	Gender:	M
Postal Address	9901 Powder Mill Rd.; Bldg.580, BARC-East; Laurel, MD 20708		
E-mail	jarred.yasuhara-bell@usda.gov		
Phone	+13013139342		

Partner 19			
Organisation	Agriculture Victoria Research, Victoria Australia		
Name of Contact (incl. Title)	Fiona Constable	Gender:	F
Postal Address	Agribio, 5 Ring Road, Bundoora, Victoria, Australia, 3083		
E-mail	Fiona.constable@agriculture.vic.gov.au		
Phone	+61 407 723 086		

2. Short project report

2.1 Short executive summary

Xylella fastidiosa is a quarantine bacterium transmitted by some xylem-feeding vectors and it is the causal agent of several diseases on economically important plants. The multiplication of the bacterium in a plant depends upon environmental factors, bacterial strains and the host plant species or cultivars. The EPPO Diagnostic Protocol PM 7/24 (5) gives some recommendations for sampling according to host plants, seasons and locations. In general, sampling should preferably be performed during the period of active growth of the plant to maximize the likelihood of detection (Hopkins, 1981). Plant analyses are required for trade prior to planting. For deciduous plant species, analysis is often required in autumn and winter, during the dormant phase. Recent experiments conducted in the framework of EU projects (POnTE, XF-ACTORS) have shown that in Mediterranean countries, *Xylella fastidiosa* can be detected in deciduous plants (such as almond and cherry trees) all year round and including the asymptomatic phases or the dormancy, the period with the lowest bacterial concentration. Although detecting *Xylella fastidiosa* in dormant plants was shown possible in some cases, the performance of the tests is dependent on the plant species and the geographical locations. The current EPPO Diagnostic Protocol PM 7/24 (5) mentions: "Experience in temperate areas shows that in grapevine or deciduous trees, e.g. cherry and almond, that have been infected for some time, the bacterium is not detected into the new season's growth until the middle of summer, when symptoms may also become visible. For example, the most suitable time for searching for symptoms in grapevine is late summer to early autumn when weather conditions are predominantly hot and dry or when grape plants are exposed to drought stress (Galvez *et al.*, 2010)." In this context, this Euphresco project aimed at evaluating the detection methods of *Xylella fastidiosa* and identification methods of subspecies of *Xylella fastidiosa* within dormant Mediterranean plants that are commercially important throughout the year and during dormancy on woody stems.

2.2 Project aims

This project aimed to provide knowledge to support the diagnosis of *Xylella fastidiosa* in dormant plants. There is a great interest in dormant wood testing as it can be done during winter for deciduous plant species, which is important for trade.

The objectives of the project were:

- to collect and share dormant plant samples naturally infected with *Xylella fastidiosa* (different subspecies, ST, plant matrices and geographical location of origin),

- to evaluate performance of several molecular tests for the detection and identification of *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies in spiked and naturally infected dormant plant samples,
- to evaluate the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* in woody stems naturally infected throughout the year including dormancy.

2.3 Description of the main activities

2.3.1 WP1: Inventory

Work Package 1 consisted of the following tasks:

- make an **inventory of dormant plants** that could be infected with *Xylella fastidiosa*, focusing on Mediterranean plants,
- evaluate whether **infected dormant plants were available for sampling** during the year,
- make an **inventory of methods** (sampling, DNA extraction, diagnostic tests) used by the different laboratories for the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* in dormant plants.

Anses prepared a survey and sent it to participants to find out:

- if they do *Xylella fastidiosa* analysis and if yes, *Xylella fastidiosa* analysis in dormant plants,
- if yes, in which context? (territory monitoring, import/export control, outbreak control, research, other), and in which species? (*Prunus dulcis*, *Vitis vinifera*, *Prunus domestica*, *Prunus avium*, *Prunus armeniaca*, other),
- what DNA extraction method is used for *Xylella fastidiosa* detection? for *Xylella fastidiosa* detection in dormant plants?
- what PCR method is used for *Xylella fastidiosa* detection and subspecies determination in dormant plants?

2.3.2 WP2: Evaluation of methods on spiked samples

Work Package 2 (conducted by CREA-DC) involved the evaluation of methods on spiked samples, with the following tasks:

- evaluate diagnostic tests in samples of dormant plant species spiked at low bacterial concentrations,
- evaluate the influence of the plant matrix collected in different periods of the year on the detection/identification of *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies.

Prunus dulcis samples were spiked with *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* (strain MQ142, ST87) and *Vitis vinifera* samples with *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* (strain Temecula 1, ST1). Comparison was done among qPCR (Harper *et al.*, 2010, *erratum* 2013), droplet digital PCR (Dupas *et al.*, 2019a), tetraplex qPCR set 2 (Dupas *et al.*, 2019b), and qPCR (Hodgetts *et al.*, 2021) in spiked samples of plant species taken during the dormancy period and other vegetative stages.

2.3.3 WP3: Evaluation of methods on naturally infected samples

Work Package 3 involved the evaluation of methods on naturally infected samples, with the following tasks:

- collect and share dormant plant material important for the Mediterranean region naturally infected with *Xylella fastidiosa*,
- evaluate diagnostic tests for the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* in dormant plants naturally infected through the organisation of a Test Performance Study (TPS),
- evaluate the distribution dynamics of *Xylella fastidiosa* in woody stems naturally infected throughout the year including dormancy.

Naturally infected dormant plant samples (woody twigs of almond and plum trees, and grapevine) were collected in France (DRAAF Occitanie), Spain (IVIA, Valencia), Italy (CNR, ISPP, Bari) and Israel (PPIS).

A TPS was organized by Anses and a total of 14 laboratories from 10 countries (EU, USA, Australia and UK) participated. During the test, the laboratories were identified by an anonymous identification code to guarantee the confidentiality of the results.

Panels sent to participants included 10 samples of dormant woody twigs naturally infected with different subspecies and sequence types of *Xylella fastidiosa* and healthy samples. The detailed composition of the panel is presented in the TPS report in the Appendix I. The homogeneity and stability of the samples were verified.

The organiser proposed a common protocol for *Xylella fastidiosa* detection (CTAB DNA extraction/Harper real-time PCR):

- CTAB is used as a 'reference extraction method' because it is widely used in most laboratories. However, laboratories may now use commercial kits for safety reasons, to allow processing with a robot and to achieve more reproducible results.

- Harper real-time PCR is used as the “reference PCR test for *Xylella fastidiosa* detection” because it is used by all laboratories.

The participants had the possibility to test other DNA extraction method and PCR protocols to detect *Xylella fastidiosa* and to determine the subspecies.

In addition, some laboratories used MLST to determine sequence types and digital PCR to detect and quantify *Xylella fastidiosa* in samples.

The protocols tested by participants are presented in the TPS report in the Appendix I.

The performance criteria (diagnostic sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, repeatability and reproducibility) for each protocol were evaluated. Following analysis of the data, only tests carried out by at least three laboratories could be validated.

A one-year monitoring of *Xylella fastidiosa*-infected almond trees in the Balearic Islands (Spain) was performed by IVIA. They compared *Xylella fastidiosa* detection in petioles and wood throughout the year.

Comparative assays of the bacterial load in different tissues (i.e. hardwood shoots and leaf petioles) of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* infected almond and cherry trees were also carried out by IPSP throughout the whole vegetative season (between May and November 2024) using field plant materials collected in the framework of the regional monitoring program carried out in Apulia (Italy) in 2023-2024. A similar comparison, but to a limited extend, was also performed for grapevine infected by *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* genotype ST1.

2.4 Main results

2.4.1 WP1: Inventory

The inventory of dormant plants was not exhaustive but plants of major interest for trade were identified through the survey conducted: almond tree, grapevine, plum tree, cherry tree and apricot tree. Infected dormant plant samples were available and collected by the different partners of the project in France, Spain, Italy and Israel.

2.4.2 WP2: Evaluation of methods on spiked samples

This study evaluated the performance of four molecular assays: qPCR Harper *et al.* (2010, erratum 2013), qPCR Hodgetts *et al.* (2021), qPCR Dupas *et al.* (2019b), and ddPCR Dupas *et al.* (2019a),

for detecting *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* and *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* in grapevine and almond matrices. Analyses were conducted across four seasonal time points (May, July, November, February) between 2023 and 2025.

Figure 1 (A, B) shows the analytical results obtained by each test in the different seasons on grape (A) and almond (B) respectively spiked with *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* and *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex*. The results obtained on spiked samples of dormant almond and grapevine at low bacterial load showed that ddPCR was consistently able to detect up to 10² CFU/mL of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* and *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* in both plant species. The high sensitivity of ddPCR was also confirmed in the other seasons/plant species evaluated showing a range of variability of 10¹-10³ CFU/mL.

A	Spiked <i>Vitis vinifera</i> / Xff February 2023-2025														
	Harper			Digital			Dupas						Hodgetts		
	2023	2024	2025	2023	2024	2025	2023		2024		2025		2023	2024	2025
							FAM	HEX	FAM	HEX	FAM	HEX			
10 ³	9/9	9/9	9/9	3/3	3/3	3/3	9/9	9/9	9/9	9/9	N.A.	9/9	9/9	9/9	9/9
10 ²	7/9	8/9	9/9	3/3	3/3	3/3	-----	-----	-----	3/9	N.A.	3/9	6/9	9/9	8/9
10 ¹	-----	2/9	2/9	2/3	3/3	2/3	-----	-----	-----	-----	N.A.	-----	-----	-----	-----

B	Spiked <i>Prunus dulcis</i> / Xfm February 2024 - 2025									
	Harper		Digital		Dupas				Hodgetts	
	2024	2025	2024	2025	2024		2025		2024	2025
					FAM	ROX	FAM	ROX		
10 ³	9/9	9/9	3/3	3/3	9/9	9/9	N.A.	9/9	9/9	9/9
10 ²	9/9	5/9	3/3	3/3	-----	3/9	N.A.	-----	9/9	5/9
10 ¹	5/9	2/9	2/3	-----	-----	-----	N.A.	-----	4/9	-----

Figure 1: Results of diagnostic tests evaluated on spiked grape (A) and almond (B) samples. The number of positive results on the total assessed is reported.

Regarding the different period tested, for both plant species, May resulted the most favorable period for monitoring purposes, with all tested methods, showing minimal interference from plant matrix-derived inhibitors, detecting up to 10² CFU/mL (except for Dupas *et al.*, 2019b).

Regarding identification from plant matrices, Hodgetts *et al.* (2021) proved to be more sensitive than Dupas, with this difference appearing random and unrelated to the seasonal period or to the plant matrix/species. These findings highlight the importance of selecting, for grape and almond, optimal sampling periods and plant matrices, as well as the appropriate molecular methods, to ensure accurate detection and timely containment.

2.4.3 WP3: Evaluation of methods on naturally infected samples

The organizer analysed the TPS results of all participants and provided a report detailing the values assigned to the samples and the results for all tested protocols. Table 1 summarizes the values obtained for the performance criteria for selected methods (tested by a minimum of three laboratories) tested in this TPS. Detailed results are presented in the TPS report in the Appendix I.

Table 1. Performance criteria values obtained for *Xylella fastidiosa* detection protocols, subspecies and ST determination protocols, tested by a minimum of three laboratories.

Performance criteria	Harper simplex			Hodgetts simplex (Xfm)	Hodgetts simplex (Xff)		Hodgetts simplex (Xfp)		Dupas tetraplex
	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
Diagnostic sensitivity	98,6	91,4	98,0	100	87,5	83,3	100	100	100
Diagnostic specificity	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Accuracy	98,9	93,3	98,4	100	97,2	94,4	100	100	100
Repeatability	97,1	97,5	98,8	100	100	100	100	100	96,8
Reproducibility	97,8	89,3	97,3	95,8	95,8	95,1	95,8	95,1	100
Number of laboratories	10	5	7	4	4	3	4	3	3

In the TPS, the “Harper simplex” PCR method was validated for the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* and the “Hodgetts simplex” and the “Dupas tetraplex” PCR methods were validated for the identification of subspecies in dormant plant samples. Other methods might also be usable to reliably detect *Xylella fastidiosa* and identify the subspecies in dormant plants but as they were tested by only one or two laboratories, they cannot be validated within the framework of an interlaboratory validation.

Concerning the one-year monitoring of *Xylella fastidiosa*-infected almond trees in the Balearic Islands (Spain) comparing detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* in petioles vs. wood samples, periodic (monthly) sampling was carried out on 16 trees in a plot infected with almond leaf scorch, with varying degrees of symptoms. Petioles and branch pieces (wood) were analysed, except in the winter months when the almond trees lost their leaves, when only the wood was evaluated. The samples were processed for PCR detection, both by Harper *et al.* (2010, *erratum* 2013) and Ouyang *et al.* (2013), and isolation on semi-selective medium. The results clearly showed that, in general, detection levels were better in wood than in petioles, as the Cq values of the PCR were earlier in wood. It is interesting to note that in some cases, a dilution of the plant extracts was necessary to be able to detect the pathogen. The earliest Cq values were obtained in December, from wood (most of the trees had lost their leaves). Although variability was found among trees, in general the pathogen was always detected in wood,

also during the tree's dormant months (when the trees had lost the leaves) (Figure 2), while petiole detection was not always successful, even though the Cq values of the wood indicated a high bacterial load in the tree (Figure 3). At the end of summer and in fall, the Cq values were fairly similar, although always slightly earlier in wood. During winter, when the almond trees had lost their leaves, the bacteria continued to be detected in wood, generally with Cq values below 25. From March onwards, it could be detected in petioles in some trees, but not in all, and in April it was detected in petioles, although with later Cq values than in wood. It is noteworthy that no obvious correlation was observed between the degree of symptomatology and the Cq values.

The bacteria could be isolated from all 16 trees in all samples taken throughout the year, both from wood and petioles.

Figure 2: Detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* in wood (brown colour) or petioles (green colour) of almond trees from an infected plot in Balearic Islands throughout one year, according to the results of PCR by Harper *et al.* (2010, *erratum* 2013). The values shown correspond to the average of 16 almond trees. In January and February, none of the trees had leaves.

Figure 3: Representative example of a tree in which *Xylella fastidiosa* was always detected in wood, but not always in leaves. In December, January and February, this tree had no leaves. The months marked with an arrow indicate that the tree did have leaves, but the bacteria was not detected in the petioles.

In southern Italy (in the Apulia region), in 2024 two new outbreaks were successfully identified by testing field trees in the dormant stage. Specifically, an outbreak of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* genotype ST1 was identified between end of January and early February 2024, on dormant vines and almond trees. In the region, *Xylella fastidiosa* monitoring program is carried out all year around for the surveillance for *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* in olives, in the framework of this program almond is also targeted for sampling being a relevant host plant for *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca*, with samples taken also during the dormancy season. The interception of *Xylella fastidiosa*-positive almond trees in early 2024, was followed by the characterization of the subspecies and the identification of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* ST1. As consequence, surveys were immediately extended to grapes, gathering positive detections and isolations from vineyards in the dormancy stage. Similarly, in early April 2024, when the almond trees were already vegetating, an additional outbreak was identified associated to the occurrence of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* genotype ST26. In this case, the detection and isolation of the bacterium occurred in the mature wood, while all the new growth tested negative.

To gather knowledge on the bacterial load in different tissues of almond (i.e. hardwood shoots and leaf petioles), comparative assays were carried out throughout the whole vegetative season (between May and November 2024) using field collected plant materials. In particular, a total of 184 almond and two cherry trees, infected with *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex*, collected in the framework of the regional monitoring program carried out in Apulia in 2023-2024, were used for the analysis.

The bacterial presence was assessed in leaf petioles and/or young portions of the apical shoots, and data were compared with those obtained from woody tissues of the same plant.

Results indicate that, even though the probability of intercepting the bacterium in leaves increases during the summer season, likely due to the higher transpiration to which trees are exposed, wooden tissues remain the most suitable matrix to analyze for diagnostic purpose since it provides a more sensitive and relatively stable diagnostic sensitivity through the season. On the contrary, leaf-based detection proved to be less sensitive with tissues collected in late spring/early summer and in early autumn, while in late summer it showed similar diagnostic sensitivity.

Notwithstanding, the dynamics of bacterial presence in almond leaves could be a useful information to be correlated with the acquisition and transmission process of insect vectors.

A similar comparison, but to a limited extent, was also performed for grapevine infected by *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* genotype ST1. In this case, due to the difficulties and restrictions to access the infected vineyard, sampling and comparative testing were limited to the autumn season (after harvesting). More specifically, in late October 2024, 160 vines from a vineyard located in the newly-demarcated *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* area were subjected to the dual analysis of wood

tissue of cuttings and leaf petioles. The results obtained mirror those retrieved from almond, with 46.25% (i.e. 74 out of 160) and 29.38% (i.e. 47 out of 160) of plants that tested *Xylella fastidiosa* positive by analyzing the wood and the petioles, respectively. Only in three cases, a leaf-based assay yielded a positive result while the corresponding wood tissue tested negative.

From this vineyard, woody canes were collected from the infected plants and used for rooting. After 3 months, rooted cuttings that had successfully sprouted were sampled to assess the movement of the bacterium from the cane to the young shoots. Results showed that, even if in a limited % of the rooted plants (21%), the bacterium was readily detectable in the young shoots (approx. 10-15cm in length).

The detection limit of the bacterium in grape wood and petioles was also evaluated in the framework of the Proficiency Test organized by CNR-IPSP in July 2024. The achieved LoD was equal to 10 CFU/mL for both matrices. However, the Cq values obtained for this dilution were > 34, values that, being close to the detection limit of the method, conventionally are associated with negative “real” samples, and can be also generated by non-specific backgrounds.

Figure 4: Bar chart of quantification cycle obtained by testing wood and leaf tissues from the same plant from May to November 2024.

2.5 Conclusions and recommendations to policy makers

Reliable methods, internationally validated for analysing *Xylella fastidiosa* throughout the year, particularly during the dormancy stage, are necessary and of great interest for the trade of plants of high economic importance (vines, prunus).

The test performance study enabled the selection of protocols that give the best results for the detection and identification of *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies in dormant plants (see TPS report in the Appendix I).

2.6 Benefits from trans-national cooperation

The main benefit from this trans-national cooperation was to build trust among European and international laboratories in order to deliver recommendations to policy makers. The collaboration allowed collecting and sharing naturally infected dormant plant samples further tested within the framework of a collaborative test performance study.

Collaboration leads the consortium to present TPS results to an important scientific and technical community during the International Conference on Plant Pathogenic Bacteria & Biocontrol 2024 in USA (Blacksburg, Virginia, July 2024). Collaboration will be easier in the future between laboratories that have worked together for more than two years.

The project demonstrated the usefulness of comparative laboratory testing for protocol validation.

References cited:

- Dupas E, Legendre B, Olivier V, Poliakoff F, Manceau C, Cuntz A (2019a) Comparison of real-time PCR and droplet digital PCR for the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* in plants. *Journal Microbiological Methods*, 162, 86-95. doi: 10.1016/j.mimet.2019.05.010. Epub 2019 May 22. PMID: 31125573.
- Dupas E, Briand M, Jacques MA, Cesbron S (2019b) Novel tetraplex quantitative PCR assays for simultaneous detection and identification of *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies in plant tissues. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10, 1732.
- Galvez LC, Korus K, Fernandez J, Behn JL, Banjara N (2010) The threat of Pierce's disease to Midwest wine and table grapes. *APSnet Features*. 2010-2015. 10.1094/APSnetFeature.
- Harper SJ, Ward LI, Clover GRG (2010, *erratum* 2013) Development of LAMP and real-time PCR methods for the rapid detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* for quarantine and field applications. *Phytopathology*, 100, 1282-1288.

- Hodgetts J, Glover R, Cole J, Hall J, Boonham N (2021) Genomics informed design of a suite of real-time PCR assays for the specific detection of each *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 131, 855-872. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.14903>.
- Hopkins DL (1981) Seasonal concentration of the Pierce's disease bacterium in grapevine stems, petioles, and leaf veins. *Phytopathology*, 71, 415. <https://doi.org/10.1094/Phyto-71-415>.
- Ouyang P, Arif M, Fletcher J, Melcher U, Ochoa Corona FM (2013) Enhanced reliability and accuracy for field deployable bioforensic detection and discrimination of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca*, causal agent of citrus variegated chlorosis using Razor Ex technology and TaqMan quantitative PCR. *PLOS One*, 8: e81647.
- PM 7/24 (5) (2023), *Xylella fastidiosa*. *EPPO Bulletin*, 53: 205–276. <https://doi.org/10.1111/epp.12923>.

3. Outreach

3.1. Article(s) for publication in journals

None

3.2. Grey literature

TPS report (see in Appendix I)

3.3. Events

- **Kick off meeting:** 30th March 2023
- **2nd meeting:** 17th April 2024
- ICPPB & Biocontrol 2024, July 7-12, 2024, Virginia Tech, Blacksburg, USA. **Poster** “Test performance study for the detection and identification of *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies in dormant plant species”
- 6th Annual EURL Workshop, 2nd October 2024. **Lecture:** “Test Performance Study (TPS) for the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* and the identification of subspecies in dormant plant species”
- 17èmes Rencontres Plantes-Bactéries, 13 au 17 Janvier 2025, Aussois. **Poster** “Test performance study for *Xylella fastidiosa* detection and subspecies identification in dormant plant species”

4. Open Euphresco data

Validation data are available in the EPPO Database on diagnostic expertise.

Appendix I Detailed TPS report

REPORT

Test performance study (TPS) for the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* and the determination of subspecies and Sequence Types in Mediterranean dormant plant species

Ref.: 23-XfDORM

June 2023 – December 2024

This report has been prepared based on the analyses of the results received by all participant laboratories.

Authors:

Anne-Laure Boutigny, Anses

Valérie Olivier, Anses

Contents:

1 GENERAL INFORMATION	23
1.1 Objectives	23
1.2 Organizers.....	23
1.3 Participating laboratories	24
1.4 Documents and instructions.....	24
1.5 Timeline	25
2. PANEL OF EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES	25
3. DIAGNOSTIC PROTOCOLS EVALUATED.....	26
4. ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS	28
5. RESULTS	30
5.1 Homogeneity and stability	30
5.1.1 Homogeneity	30
5.1.2 Stability.....	31
5.2 Results of the TPS	31
5.2.1 Qualitative results	32
5.2.2 Quantitative results.....	45
6. SUMMARY OF THE OVERALL VALUES OBTAINED FOR EACH OF THE PERFORMANCE CRITERIA	47
7 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION	47
8. REFERENCES.....	49
9. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	50
Annex I.....	51
Annex II.....	52
Annex III.....	57

1 GENERAL INFORMATION

1.1 Objectives

This test performance study (TPS) was organized in 2023 as part of the **Euphresco project 2022-A-406 entitled “Diagnosis of *Xylella fastidiosa*: detection on dormant plants, important for Mediterranean countries”** to evaluate the performance of several molecular protocols for the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* and the determination of subspecies and sequence types (ST) in naturally infected dormant plant samples. There is a great interest in analyses on dormant wood, particularly during the winter period or for trade. The TPS was organized in accordance with the EPPO PM7/122 guidelines.

Panels of samples sent to participants included dormant woody twigs naturally infected with *X. fastidiosa* and healthy ones. Twigs were from almond and plum trees, and grapevine, and were collected in France, Italy, Spain or Israel in order to have different sources of infection (*X. fastidiosa* subspecies and sequence types), plant species and plant cultivars. For this TPS, samples were pre-tested and prepared by Anses. Then panels of samples were sent to the participating laboratories for analysis. A common protocol for *X. fastidiosa* detection (CTAB DNA extraction/Harper real-time PCR) was proposed by the organizer and it was possible for participants to test other DNA extraction and PCR protocols to detect *X. fastidiosa* and determine the subspecies. In addition, some laboratories tested MLST to determine the sequence types and digital PCR to detect and quantify *X. fastidiosa*. The diagnostic protocols are described in the EPPO diagnostic protocol PM 7/24 (5) and/or in the technical sheet sent to participating laboratories (**Annex I**).

The performance criteria (diagnostic sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, repeatability and reproducibility) for each protocol were evaluated. The organizer analyzed the results of all participants and provided a report detailing the values assigned to the samples and the results for all protocols.

1.2 Organizers

This TPS was organized by the **French Agency for food, environmental and occupational health and safety (Anses)**, Plant health laboratory, Bacteriology Virology and GMO detection unit (Angers, France).

1.3 Participating laboratories

A total of 14 laboratories from 10 countries participated in the TPS (Table 1). During the test, they were identified by an anonymous identification code to guarantee the confidentiality of the results.

Table 1. Laboratories participating in TPS 23-XfDorm

Laboratories	Country
US Department of Agriculture, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service (USDA)	USA
NSW Department of Primary Industries and Regional Development & Department of Agriculture, Water and the Environment	Australia
Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO)	Belgium
Science and Advice for Scottish Agriculture (SASA)	United Kingdom
National Institute of Biology (NIB)	Slovenia
Valencian Institute for Agricultural Research (IVIA)	Spain
Forest Research	United Kingdom
Agdia, Inc.	USA
French Agency for food, environmental and occupational health and safety (ANSES)	France
Fera Science (FERA)	United Kingdom
Council for agronomic research and economic analysis (CREA)	Italy
Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	Ireland
Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA)	Netherlands
Instituute for sustainable Plant Protection (IPSP)	Italy

1.4 Documents and instructions

Participants received the following documents containing the **contract, instructions and descriptions of the panel of samples and protocols** to be used:

- Instructions and Technical sheet (**Annex I**)
- Participant contract (**Annex II**)
- Excel files with result sheet form to report the results

1.5 Timeline

The sample panels (sent to the participating laboratories and used for homogeneity and stability tests) were prepared between 3 March and 15 May 2023. The homogeneity tests were performed at Anses on 14 and 16 March 2023, immediately after the preparation of the different samples.

The panels of samples were then stored at -20°C prior to shipment. The shipment was organized on 22 May 2023. The stability tests were performed at Anses on 6 June 2023, after all TPS packages had been received by all laboratories.

Participants were asked to perform their selected diagnostic protocols and send the results to the organizers by 28 July 2023. All raw data (qualitative and quantitative results) received from the participating laboratories were compiled in separate Excel files. The final report was completed and submitted in December 2024.

2. PANEL OF EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES

Each panel consisted of **10 samples of dormant woody twigs naturally infected with *X. fastidiosa* and not infected**. Each sample of dormant woody twigs was cut into 2 cm pieces. After homogenization of all pieces by hand, 10 pieces (three large, four medium and three thin) were randomly selected to form a sample (see photo).

Each panel of samples shipped to each laboratory included (Table 2):

- one sample of almond tree not infected (from France)
- one sample of grapevine not infected (from France)
- one sample of plum tree infected with *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* (from Occitanie, France)
- three samples of almond tree infected with *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* (one from France, two from Spain)
- one sample of almond tree infected with *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* (from Puglia, Italy)
- two samples of grapevine infected with *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* (from Israel)

- one lure sample (a duplicate of one of the samples, different for each laboratory)

Samples in each panel were coded (**Annex III**) to ensure that results were not shared between laboratories.

Table 2. Samples included in each panel

Panel					
Samples	Plant species	Country	Assigned value	Subspecies	ST
A	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	France	-	/	/
B	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	France	+	<i>multiplex</i>	6
C	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Spain	+	<i>multiplex</i>	6
D	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Spain	+	<i>multiplex</i>	6
E	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Italy	+	<i>pauca</i>	53
F	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	France	+	<i>multiplex</i>	6
G	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	France	-	/	/
H	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Israel	+	<i>fastidiosa</i>	1
I	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Israel	+	<i>fastidiosa</i>	1
J	Lure	duplicate of one sample, different for each laboratory			

3. DIAGNOSTIC PROTOCOLS EVALUATED

The TPS included the testing of different DNA extraction methods and molecular methods proposed in the EPPO standard PM7/24 (5) for the detection of *X. fastidiosa* and/or the determination of subspecies and sequence type (ST).

The following protocols were tested by the laboratories:

- DNA extraction methods:
 - CTAB (EPPO PM7/24 (5))
 - QuickPick™ SML Plant DNA kit (QRET Technologies) (EPPO PM7/24 (5))
 - DNeasy Plant Mini Kit (Qiagen) (EPPO PM7/24 (5))
 - Other DNA extraction methods (selected by participants): Maxwell® HT Environmental TNA (Promega), Maxwell RSC PureFood GMO (Promega), DNeasy® Mericon™ Food Standard Protocol (Qiagen)
- Molecular methods for *X. fastidiosa* detection:
 - Real-time PCR Harper *et al.* (2010) (EPPO PM7/24 (5)): simplex and/or duplex
 - Other PCR for *X. fastidiosa* detection (selected by participants): Bonants *et al.* (2019), NSW DPI endpoint, Agdia AmplifyXRT+
- Molecular methods for *X. fastidiosa* DNA quantification:

- Digital PCR Dupas *et al.* (2019a)
- Molecular methods for subspecies determination:
 - Tetraplex real-time PCR Dupas *et al.* (2019b) (EPPO PM7/24 (5))
 - Simplex real-time PCR Dupas *et al.* (2019b)
 - Real-time PCR Hodgetts *et al.* (2021) (EPPO PM7/24 (5))
- Molecular methods for ST determination:
 - MLST Yuan *et al.* (2010) recommended on 7 genes (EPPO PM7/24 (5))

The DNA extraction methods, thermocycler information and molecular methods tested by each laboratory are presented in Tables 3, 4 and 5. **Laboratory numbers (1, 2, 3, ...) in Tables 3, 4 and 5 are different from laboratory codes (L01, L02, L03, ...) to ensure confidentiality of the results in this report.**

Table 3. Thermocyclers and protocols tested by laboratories for detection of *X. fastidiosa*

Laboratory	Thermocycler	Harper simplex				
		CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	Maxwell	DNeasy Mericon Food Kit ^c
1	QuantStudio 5 (Applied Biosystems)	x	x			
2	QuantStudio 6 (Applied Biosystems)	x		x		
3	QuantStudio 3 (Applied Biosystems)	x				
4 ^a	LightCycler 480 II (Roche)		x	x		
5	CFX96 (BioRad)	x	x			
6 ^a	QuantStudio 7 (Applied Biosystems)	x	x			
7	CFX96 (BioRad)	x		x		
8	QuantStudio 5 (Applied Biosystems)	x		x		
9	CFX96 (BioRad)			x		
10	CFX96 (BioRad)	x		x	x	
11 ^a	CFX96 (BioRad)	x			x	x
12	ViiA 7 (Applied Biosystems)			x		
13	QuantStudio 5 (Applied Biosystems)	x ^b				
14	QuantStudio 5 (Applied Biosystems)		x ^b			

^a no sonication

^b 2 Taq polymerase tested: TaqMan Fast Universal PCR Master Mix (Applied Biosystems) / PerfeCTa qPCR ToughMix (Quantabio)

^c Modified DNeasy Mericon Food Standard Protocol (Qiagen)

Laboratory	Thermocycler	Harper duplex		Bonants (Target Harper - FAM)	Bonants (Target Ouyang - HEX)	NSWDPI endpoint		Agdia AmplifyXRT+
		DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	CTAB	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit
1	QuantStudio 5 (Applied Biosystems)					x	x	
3	QuantStudio 3 (Applied Biosystems)			x	x			
4 ^a	LightCycler 480 II (Roche)	x	x					
5	CFX96 (BioRad)							x
10	CFX96 (BioRad)		x					

^a no sonication

Table 4. Thermocyclers and protocols tested by laboratories for detection and quantification of *X. fastidiosa* using Digital PCR

Laboratory	Thermocycler	Digital PCR		
		CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	Maxwell
2	QX200 (BioRad)	x	x	
10	QX200 (BioRad)	x		
11	QX200 (BioRad)			x

Table 5. Thermocyclers and protocols tested by laboratories for determination of *X. fastidiosa* subspecies and ST

Laboratory	Thermocycler	Hodgetts simplex			Dupas simplex	
		CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
3	Hodgetts: QuantStudio 3 (AB) triplex: LighCycler 480 II (Roche)	x				
6 ^a	QuantStudio 7 (Applied Biosystems)	x	x			
7	CFX96 (BioRad)	x		x		
8	QuantStudio 5 (AB)	x		x	x	x
12	ViiA 7 (AB)			x		
13	QuantStudio 5 (AB)				x	

^a no sonication

Laboratory	Thermocycler	Dupas triplex	Dupas tetraplex		MLST		
		CTAB	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	Maxwell
1	QuantStudio 5 (Applied Biosystems)		x				
2	tetraplex: CFX96 (BioRad) MLST: Veriti (AB)		x	x	x	x	
3	Hodgetts: QuantStudio 3 (AB) triplex: LighCycler 480 II (Roche)	x					
7	CFX96 (BioRad)		x ^b	x ^b			
8	QuantStudio 5 (AB)		x	x			
10	CFX96 (BioRad)			x			x

^b 2 Taq polymerase tested: SsoAdvanced Universal Probes Supermix (BioRad) / Brilliant Multiplex qPCR Master Mix (Agilent)

4. ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

The results were analyzed on the basis of qualitative data (negative, positive, undetermined) and some quantitative data (Cq values). In each laboratory, samples were categorized as negative, positive or undetermined, according to the Cq values obtained. For each laboratory, the organizer determined the number of positive agreements (PA), negative agreements (NA), positive deviations (PD) and negative deviations (ND) according to the modalities described in Table 6. The performance criteria (Table 7) were then calculated from the recorded values for each protocol (Chabirand *et al.*, 2014 for more detailed information).

Table 6. Definition of modalities based on ISO 16140

Test results	Assigned value	
	Positive	Negative
Positive	PA = positive agreement	PD = positive deviation
Negative	ND = negative deviation	NA = negative agreement

Table 7. Details of performance criteria

Performance criteria	Definition	Calculation
Sensitivity (SE)	Closeness of agreement between the test result and the assigned value for samples for which the assigned value is positive	$SE = N_{PA}/N_{+}$
Specificity (SP)	Closeness of agreement between the test result and the assigned value for samples for which the assigned value is negative	$SP = N_{NA}/N_{-}$
Accuracy (AC)	Closeness of agreement between the test result and the assigned value	$AC = (N_{PA} + N_{NA})/N$
Repeatability (DA)	Closeness of agreement between independent test results obtained under conditions of repeatability, i.e. conditions under which independent test results are obtained by the same method, on identical test samples in the same laboratory, by the same operator, using the same equipment, within a short period of time	DA denotes the percentage chance of obtaining the same result (positive, negative or indeterminate) from two identical samples analyzed with the same protocol
Reproducibility	The reproducibility is the probability of finding the same result for two identical samples analyzed in two different laboratories	The % of reproducibility is calculated based on the number of interlaboratory pairs of same results/total number of interlaboratory pairs

5. RESULTS

5.1 Homogeneity and stability

Homogeneity tests were performed before samples were shipped, while stability tests were performed after all laboratories had received their samples. The homogeneity and the stability tests were assessed using the duplex real-time PCR Harper/loos following DNA extraction with the QuickPick™ SML Plant DNA kit. The Cq values obtained during the homogeneity and stability tests are reported in Table 8. The average Cq values obtained by seven participant laboratories using the real-time PCR Harper following DNA extraction with the QuickPick™ SML Plant DNA kit are also reported for each sample.

Table 8. Cq values obtained during the homogeneity and stability tests and average Cq values obtained by the participating laboratories. SD indicates the standard deviation.

Panel				All laboratories		Homogeneity		Stability	
Samples	Plant species	Country	Status	Average	SD	Average	SD	Average	SD
A	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	France	-	neg	/	neg	/	neg	/
B	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	France	+	27,39	0,89	28,99	0,51	30,90	0,21
C	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Spain	+	29,07	1,03	29,13	0,19	28,32	0,19
D	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Spain	+	29,70	2,01	31,23	0,47	28,19	0,06
E	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Italy	+	31,00	1,67	33,06	0,42	32,47	0,22
F	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	France	+	29,69	1,00	30,86	0,34	31,48	0,07
G	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	France	-	neg	/	neg	/	neg	/
H	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Israël	+	31,56	1,32	33,58	0,29	36,75	0,83
I	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Israël	+	29,34	2,03	30,60	0,43	30,63	0,08

The results obtained were qualitatively validated. *X. fastidiosa* was not detected in expected negative samples and was detected in expected positive samples. The detailed results and calculations for homogeneity and stability are presented in Tables 9 and 10.

5.1.1 Homogeneity

The homogeneity study involved 9 samples (A to I, Table 2). To assess the average contamination rate of samples, 10 pieces of twigs about 2 cm long were selected at random from each sample, cut and homogenized. Then, three macerates (A, B and C) were prepared for each sample and three DNA extractions (Ext 1, 2 and 3) were performed for each macerate and analyzed (two PCR replicates). **According to the ISO 13528 standard, all qualitative and quantitative results were homogeneous.**

Table 9. Homogeneity results

Homogeneity panel				Macerate A			Macerate B			Macerate C			Status	Average Cq	SD
Samples	Plant species	Country	Status	Ext 1	Ext 2	Ext 3	Ext 1	Ext 2	Ext 3	Ext 1	Ext 2	Ext 3			
A	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	France	-	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	-	neg	/
B	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	France	+	29,27	29,34	29,49	29,32	29,41	29,10	28,26	28,35	28,39	+	28,99	0,51
C	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Spain	+	28,94	29,29	29,24	29,43	29,29	29,10	28,96	28,91	29,01	+	29,13	0,19
D	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Spain	+	30,60	30,95	30,80	31,15	31,24	30,91	31,74	31,89	31,78	+	31,23	0,47
E	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Italy	+	33,00	32,29	32,60	33,28	33,44	33,58	33,27	33,20	32,85	+	33,06	0,42
F	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	France	+	30,75	30,69	30,43	30,80	30,39	31,05	30,95	31,42	31,22	+	30,86	0,34
G	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	France	-	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	neg	-	neg	/
H	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Israël	+	33,64	33,12	33,68	33,78	33,74	33,96	33,21	33,32	33,79	+	33,58	0,29
I	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Israël	+	30,14	30,22	30,04	30,89	31,15	31,01	31,04	30,47	30,42	+	30,60	0,43

5.1.2 Stability

The stability study involved 9 samples (A to I, Table 2). One macerate was prepared for each sample and 2 DNA extractions (Ext 1 and Ext 2) were performed for each macerate and analyzed (2 PCR replicates). The results were compared with the Cq values obtained in the homogeneity study. **According to the ISO 13528 standard, all qualitative results were stable.** Quantitative results were stable for samples A, C, E, F, G and I and were not stable for samples B, D and H.

Table 10. Stability results

Stability panel				Ext 1		Ext 2		Status	Average Cq	SD	Qualitative stability	Quantitative stability
Samples	Plant species	Country	Status	PCR 1	PCR2	PCR 1	PCR2					
A	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	France	-	neg	neg	neg	neg	-	neg	/	yes	yes
B	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	France	+	31,09	31,07	30,76	30,66	+	30,90	0,21	yes	no
C	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Spain	+	28,52	28,44	28,12	28,20	+	28,32	0,19	yes	yes
D	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Spain	+	28,15	28,28	28,20	28,15	+	28,19	0,06	yes	no
E	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Italy	+	32,52	32,48	32,17	32,71	+	32,47	0,22	yes	yes
F	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	France	+	31,38	31,47	31,54	31,51	+	31,48	0,07	yes	yes
G	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	France	-	neg	neg	neg	neg	-	neg	/	yes	yes
H	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Israël	+	35,74	37,38	36,40	37,47	+	36,75	0,83	yes	no
I	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	Israël	+	30,55	30,57	30,70	30,70	+	30,63	0,08	yes	yes

5.2 Results of the TPS

It is important to note that the following rules were used to determine the positivity threshold of the samples for the different methods (as defined in Harper *et al.* (2010)):

- Real-time PCR Harper *et al.* (2010): positive result if Cq value ≤ 38
- Duplex real-time PCR Harper *et al.* (2010) / loos *et al.* (2009): positive result if Cq value ≤ 38

The following rules were also used to determine whether samples were positive or negative:

PCR results		Final decision
Ext 1	Ext 2	
+/+	+/+	+
+/+	+/-	+
+/+	-/-	+
+/-	+/-	+
+/-	-/-	-
-/-	-/-	-

According to these decision rules, the results (positive/negative) sent by the participants were harmonized in some cases.

In addition, we decided to exclude some of the data:

- L10 : exclusion of the results obtained with the Dupas tetraplex PCR (following CTAB and QP DNA extractions) due to cross reactions of some fluorophores using the QuantStudio 5 thermocycler
- L01 : exclusion of the results obtained with the Dupas tetraplex PCR (following CTAB DNA extraction) due to insufficient data (only one extraction)
- L03 : exclusion of sample I (CTAB DNA extraction) because of contamination with *X. fastidiosa* subsp *multiplex*
- L05 : exclusion of sample H (CTAB DNA extraction/Harper simplex PCR) because inhibition was demonstrated in this sample by the laboratory

5.2.1 Qualitative results

In this TPS, three *X. fastidiosa* detection protocols (CTAB/Harper PCR simplex, DNeasy/Harper PCR simplex and Quickpick/Harper PCR simplex) and three subspecies determination protocols (CTAB/Hodgetts PCR simplex, Quickpick/Hodgetts PCR simplex and Quickpick/Dupas PCR tetraplex) were tested by a large number of laboratories (more than three) and all performance criteria were calculated. For the other protocols used by less than three laboratories, only the diagnostic sensitivity, diagnostic specificity and accuracy were calculated.

Diagnostic sensitivity

1) Diagnostic sensitivity for *X. fastidiosa* detection

The Harper simplex PCR method following CTAB, DNeasy and Quickpick DNA extractions is validated to detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants (Table 11). Sensitivity results were good after CTAB DNA extraction (98.6%, tested by 10 laboratories), after DNeasy DNA extraction (91.4%, tested by five laboratories) and after

Quickpick DNA extraction (98%, tested by seven laboratories). The lack of sensitivity is not linked to the method: sample H was not detected by one laboratory (L10) using CTAB and Quickpick DNA extractions and one laboratory (L05) had no experience with the DNeasy DNA extraction method. We cannot exclude that sample H was slightly less contaminated on some panels as these are naturally infected samples.

Table 11. Diagnostic sensitivity (%) for *X. fastidiosa* detection

Laboratory code	Harper simplex		
	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
L01	100	100	
L02 ^b	100		100
L03	100		
L04 ^a		100	100
L05	100	57,1	
L08 ^a	100	100	
L09	100		100
L10	85,7		85,7
L11			100
L13	100		100
L15 ^a	100		
L16			100
L17	100		
L18		100	
All laboratories	98,6	91,4	98,0
N	10	5	7

^a no sonication

^b this laboratory used TaqMan Environmental Master Mix 2.0 (AB)

^c Modified DNeasy Mericon Food Standard Protocol

Laboratory code	Harper simplex		Harper duplex		Bonants (target Harper - FAM)	Bonants (target Ouyang - HEX)	NSWDPI endpoint		Agdia AmplifyXRT+	Dupas triplex (Xf)	Dupas simplex (Xf)
	Maxwell	DNeasy Mericon Food Kit ^c	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	CTAB	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	CTAB	CTAB
L01							85,7	100			
L03					100	100				83,3	
L04 ^a			100	100							
L05									57,1		
L13	100			100							
L15 ^a	100	100									
L17											85,7
All laboratories	100	100	100	100	100	100	85,7	100	57,1	83,3	85,7
N	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

^a no sonication

^c Modified DNeasy Mericon Food Standard Protocol (Qiagen)

The following detection protocols are usable to reliably detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one or two laboratories: Maxwell/Harper simplex, DNeasy Mericon/Harper simplex, DNeasy/Harper duplex, Quickpick/Harper duplex, CTAB/Bonants (target Harper and target Ouyang), DNeasy/NSWDPI Endpoint.

Some protocols presented a lack of sensitivity to detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one laboratory: CTAB/NSWDPI Endpoint, DNeasy/Agdia Amplify XRT+, CTAB/Dupas triplex (Xf) and CTAB/Dupas simplex (Xf).

2) Diagnostic sensitivity for *X. fastidiosa* subspecies and ST determination

The Hodgetts simplex PCR method following CTAB and Quickpick DNA extractions is validated to determine the subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants (Table 12). Sensitivity results were good to determine *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* (Xfm) (100% following CTAB and Quickpick DNA extractions), *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* (Xff) (87.5% following CTAB and 83.3% following Quickpick DNA extractions) and *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* (Xfp) (100% following CTAB and Quickpick DNA extractions). The lack of sensitivity is not linked to the method: Xff was not detected in sample H by one laboratory (L10) using CTAB and Quickpick DNA extractions. We cannot exclude that sample H was slightly less contaminated on some panels as these are naturally infected samples.

The Dupas tetraplex PCR method following Quickpick DNA extraction is validated to determine the subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants after being tested by three laboratories (Table 12).

Table 12. Diagnostic sensitivity (%) for *X. fastidiosa* subspecies and ST determination

Laboratory code	Hodgetts simplex (Xfm)		Hodgetts simplex (Xff)		Hodgetts simplex (Xfp)		Dupas tetraplex ^f
	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
L02 ^b							100
L03	100		100		100		
L08 ^a	100		100		100		
L09	100	^d	100	100	100	100	100
L10	100	100	50	50	100	100	
L13							100
L16		100		100		100	
All laboratories	100	100	87,5	83,3	100	100	100
N	4	2	4	3	4	3	3

^a no sonication

^b This laboratory used JumpStart™ Taq ReadyMix™ (Sigma)

^d no Hodgetts simplex for Xfm

^f Dupas tetraplex: different sets used

Laboratory code	Hodgetts simplex (Xfm)	Hodgetts simplex (Xff)	Hodgetts simplex (Xfp)	Dupas simplex (Xff)		Dupas simplex (Xfm)		Dupas simplex (Xfp)		Dupas triplex ^e	Dupas tetraplex ^f	MLST		
	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit			CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	CTAB	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	Maxwell
L02 ^b											100			
L03										100				
L08 ^a	100	100	100											
L09											71,4			
L10				50	50	100	100	100	100					
L13														100
L17				50		100		100						
All laboratories	100	100	100	50	50	100	100	100	100	100	85,7	85,7	100	100
N	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1

^a no sonication

^b This laboratory used JumpStart™ Taq ReadyMix™ (Sigma)

^e Dupas triplex : FAM for Xf ; HEX for Xff and Xf-sl ; Cy5 and Cy5.5 for Xfmo; Xfp and Xfm respectively

^f Dupas tetraplex: different sets used

The following protocols are usable to reliably determine subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* or ST in dormant plants but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one or two laboratories: DNeasy/Hodgetts (Xfm, Xff and Xfp), CTAB/Dupas simplex (Xfm), Quickpick/Dupas simplex (Xfm), CTAB/Dupas simplex (Xfp), Quickpick/Dupas simplex (Xfp), CTAB/Dupas triplex, Quickpick/MLST, Maxwell/MLST.

Some protocols presented a lack of sensitivity to determine the subspecies or ST of *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one or two laboratories: CTAB/Dupas simplex (Xff), Quickpick/Dupas simplex (Xff), CTAB/Dupas tetraplex and CTAB/MLST.

3) Diagnostic sensitivity for *X. fastidiosa* detection using digital PCR

The digital PCR method following CTAB, Quickpick or Maxwell DNA extractions is usable to reliably detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants but was not validated in interlaboratory comparison because each protocol has only been tested by one or two laboratories (Table 13).

Table 13. Diagnostic sensitivity (%) for *X. fastidiosa* detection using digital PCR

Laboratory code	Digital PCR		
	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	Maxwell
L02	100	100	
L13	100		
L15			100
All laboratories	100	100	100
N	2	1	1

Diagnostic specificity

1) Diagnostic specificity for *X. fastidiosa* detection

The Harper simplex PCR method following CTAB, DNeasy and Quickpick DNA extractions gave negative results in healthy dormant plants (Table 14). Specificity results were good (100%) following CTAB DNA extraction (tested by 10 laboratories), following DNeasy DNA extraction (tested by five laboratories) and following Quickpick DNA extraction (tested by seven laboratories).

Table 14. Diagnostic specificity (%) for *X. fastidiosa* detection

Laboratory code	Harper simplex		
	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
L01	100	100	
L02 ^b	100		100
L03	100		
L04 ^a		100	100
L05	100	100	
L08 ^a	100	100	
L09	100		100
L10	100		100
L11			100
L13	100		100
L15 ^a	100		
L16			100
L17	100		
L18		100	
All laboratories	100	100	100
N	10	5	7

^a no sonication

^b this laboratory used TaqMan Environmental Master Mix 2.0 (AB)

^c Modified DNeasy Mericon Food Standard Protocol

Laboratory code	Harper simplex		Harper duplex		Bonants (target Harper - FAM)	Bonants (target Ouyang - HEX)	NSWDPI endpoint		Agdia AmplifyXRT+	Dupas triplex
	Maxwell	Dneasy Mericon Food Kit ^c	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	CTAB	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	CTAB
L01							100	100		
L03					100	100				100
L04 ^a			100	100						
L05									100	
L13	100			100						
L15 ^a	100	100								
All laboratories	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
N	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1

^a no sonication

^c Modified DNeasy Mericon Food Standard Protocol

The following protocols reliably gave negative results in healthy dormant plants but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one or two laboratories: Maxwell/Harper simplex, DNeasy Mericon/Harper simplex, DNeasy/Harper duplex, Quickpick/Harper duplex, CTAB/Bonants (target Harper and target Ouyang), CTAB/NSWDPI Endpoint, DNeasy/NSWDPI Endpoint, DNeasy/Agdia Amplify XRT+, CTAB/Dupas triplex.

2) Diagnostic specificity for *X. fastidiosa* subspecies and ST determination

The Hodgetts simplex PCR method following CTAB and Quickpick DNA extractions gave negative results in healthy dormant plants and plants infected with a non-targeted subspecies after being tested by four and three laboratories respectively (Table 15).

The Dupas tetraplex method following Quickpick DNA extraction gave negative results in healthy dormant plants and plants infected with a non-targeted subspecies after being tested by three laboratories (Table 15).

Table 15. Diagnostic specificity (%) for *X. fastidiosa* subspecies and ST determination

Laboratory code	Hodgetts simplex (Xfm)		Hodgetts simplex (Xff)		Hodgetts simplex (Xfp)		Dupas tetraplex ^f
	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
L02 ^b							100
L03	100		100		100		
L08 ^a	100		100		100		
L09	100	^d	100	100 ^c	100	100 ^c	100
L10	100	100	100	100	100	100	
L13							100
L16		100		100		100	
All laboratories	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
N	4	2	4	3	4	3	3

^a no sonication

^b this laboratory used JumpStart™ Taq ReadyMix™ (Sigma)

^d no Hodgetts simplex for Xfm

^f Dupas tetraplex: different sets used

Laboratory code	Hodgetts simplex (Xfm)	Hodgetts simplex (Xff)	Hodgetts simplex (Xfp)	Dupas simplex (Xff)		Dupas simplex (Xfm)		Dupas simplex (Xfp)		Dupas triplex ^e	Dupas tetraplex ^f	MLST		
	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	CTAB	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	Maxwell
L02 ^b											100	100	100	
L03										100				
L08 ^a	100	100	100											
L09											100			
L10				100	100	100	100	100	100					
L13														100
L17				100		100		100						
All laboratories	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
N	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1

^a no sonication

^b this laboratory used JumpStart™ Taq ReadyMix™ (Sigma)

^e Dupas triplex: FAM for Xf; HEX for Xff and Xf-si; Cy5 and Cy5.5 for Xfmo; Xfp and Xfm respectively

^f Dupas tetraplex: different sets used

The following protocols reliably gave negative results in healthy dormant plants and plants infected with a non-targeted subspecies but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one or two laboratories: DNeasy/Hodgetts, CTAB/Dupas simplex (Xff, Xfm, Xfp), Quickpick/Dupas simplex (Xff, Xfm, Xfp), CTAB/Dupas triplex, CTAB/Dupas tetraplex, CTAB/MLST, Quickpick/MLST, Maxwell/MLST.

3) Diagnostic specificity for *X. fastidiosa* detection using digital PCR

The digital PCR method following CTAB, Quickpick or Maxwell DNA extractions gave negative results in healthy dormant plants but was not validated in interlaboratory comparison because each protocol has only been tested by one or two laboratories (Table 16).

Table 16. Diagnostic specificity (%) for *X. fastidiosa* detection using digital PCR

Laboratory code	Digital PCR		
	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	Maxwell
L02	100	100	
L13	100		
L15			100
All laboratories	100	100	100
N	2	1	1

Accuracy

1) Accuracy for *X. fastidiosa* detection

The Harper simplex PCR method following CTAB, DNeasy and Quickpick DNA extractions is validated to detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants (Table 17). Accuracy of results was good following CTAB DNA extraction (98.9%) tested by 10 laboratories, following DNeasy DNA extraction (93.3%) tested by five laboratories and following Quickpick DNA extraction (98.4%) tested by seven laboratories. The lack in accuracy is not related to the method: sample H was not detected by one laboratory (L10) with the CTAB and Quickpick DNA extractions and one laboratory (L05) had no experience with the DNeasy DNA extraction method. We cannot exclude that sample H was slightly less contaminated on some panels as these are naturally infected samples.

Table 17. Accuracy (%) for *X. fastidiosa* detection

Laboratory code	Harper simplex		
	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
L01	100	100	
L02 ^b	100		100
L03	100		
L04 ^a		100	100
L05	100	66,7	
L08 ^a	100	100	
L09	100		100
L10	88,9		88,9
L11			100
L13	100		100
L15 ^a	100		
L16			100
L17	100		
L18		100	
All laboratories	98,9	93,3	98,4
N	10	5	7

^a no sonication

^b this laboratory used TaqMan Environmental Master Mix 2.0 (AB)

^c Modified DNeasy Mericon Food Standard Protocol

Laboratory code	Harper simplex		Harper duplex		Bonants (target Harper - FAM)	Bonants (target Ouyang - HEX)	NSWDPI endpoint		Agdia AmplifyXRT+	Dupas triplex	Dupas simplex (Xf)
	Maxwell	Dneasy Mericon Food Kit ^c	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	CTAB	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	CTAB	CTAB
L01							88,9	100			
L03					100	100				87,5	
L04 ^a			100	100							
L05									66,7		
L13	100			100							
L15 ^a	100	100									
L17											85,7
All laboratories	100	100	100	100	100	100	88,9	100	66,7	87,5	85,7
N	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

^a no sonication

^c Modified DNeasy Mericon Food Standard Protocol

The following protocols are usable to reliably detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one or two laboratories: Maxwell/Harper simplex, DNeasy Mericon/Harper simplex, DNeasy/Harper duplex, Quickpick/Harper duplex, CTAB/Bonants (target Harper and target Ouyang), DNeasy/NSWDPI Endpoint.

Some protocols presented a lack of accuracy to detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one laboratory: CTAB/NSWDPI Endpoint, Dneasy/Agdia Amplify XRT+, CTAB/Dupas triplex (Xf) and CTAB/Dupas simplex (Xf).

2) Accuracy for *X. fastidiosa* subspecies and ST determination

The Hodgetts simplex PCR method following CTAB and Quickpick DNA extractions is validated to determine the subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants (Table 18). Accuracy of results was good to determine Xfm (100%), Xfp (100%) and Xff (97.2% and 94.4%) following CTAB or Quickpick DNA extractions used by four and three laboratories respectively. The lack of accuracy is not linked to the method: Xff was not detected in sample H by one laboratory (L10) using CTAB and Quickpick DNA extractions. We cannot exclude that sample H was slightly less contaminated on some panels as these are naturally infected samples.

The Dupas tetraplex PCR method following Quickpick DNA extraction is validated to determine the subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants after being tested by three laboratories (Table 18).

Table 18. Accuracy (%) for *X. fastidiosa* subspecies and ST determination

Laboratory code	Hodgetts simplex (Xfm)		Hodgetts simplex (Xff)		Hodgetts simplex (Xfp)		Dupas tetraplex ^f
	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
L02 ^b							100
L03	100		100		100		
L08 ^a	100		100		100		
L09	100	^d	100	100 ^c	100	100 ^c	100
L10	100	100	88,9	88,9	100	100	
L13							100
L16		100		100		100	
All laboratories	100	100	97,2	94,4	100	100	100
N	4	2	4	3	4	3	3

^a no sonication

^b this laboratory used JumpStart™ Taq ReadyMix™ (Sigma)

^d no Hodgetts simplex for Xfm

^f Dupas tetraplex: different sets used

Laboratory code	Hodgetts simplex (Xfm)	Hodgetts simplex (Xff)	Hodgetts simplex (Xfp)	Dupas simplex (Xff)		Dupas simplex (Xfm)		Dupas simplex (Xfp)		Dupas triplex ^e	Dupas tetraplex ^f	MLST		
	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	CTAB	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	Maxwell
L02 ^b											100	88,9	100	
L03										100				
L08 ^a	100	100	100											
L09											77,8			
L10				88,9	88,9	100	100	100	100					
L13														100
L17				85,7		100		100						
All laboratories	100	100	100	87,3	88,9	100	100	100	100	100	88,9	88,9	100	100
N	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1

^a no sonication

^b this laboratory used JumpStart™ Taq ReadyMix™ (Sigma)

^c Dupas triplex : FAM for Xf ; HEX for Xff and Xf-sl ; Cy5 and Cy5.5 for Xfmo; Xfp and Xfm respectively

^d Dupas tetraplex: different sets used

The following protocols are usable to reliably determine subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* or ST in dormant plants but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one or two laboratories: DNeasy/Hodgetts (Xfm, Xff and Xfp), CTAB/Dupas simplex (Xfm), Quickpick/Dupas simplex (Xfm), CTAB/Dupas simplex (Xfp), Quickpick/Dupas simplex (Xfp), CTAB/Dupas triplex, Quickpick/MLST, Maxwell/MLST.

Some protocols presented a lack of accuracy to determine the subspecies or ST of *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants but were not validated in interlaboratory comparison because they have only been tested by one or two laboratories: CTAB/Dupas simplex (Xff), Quickpick/Dupas simplex (Xff), CTAB/Dupas tetraplex and CTAB/MLST.

3) Accuracy for *X. fastidiosa* detection using digital PCR

The digital PCR method following CTAB, Quickpick or Maxwell DNA extractions is usable to reliably detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants but was not validated in interlaboratory comparison because each protocol has only been tested by one or two laboratories (Table 19).

Table 19. Accuracy (%) for *X. fastidiosa* detection using digital PCR

Laboratory code	Digital PCR		
	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	Maxwell
L02	100	100	
L13	100		
L15			100
All laboratories	100	100	100
N	2	1	1

Comparison of Taq polymerase

Some laboratories used the panel samples to compare different Taq DNA polymerases (Table 20).

Table 20. Comparison of Taq Polymerases on the performance criteria of the Harper simplex PCR and Dupas tetraplex PCR methods

Performance criteria	Harper simplex PCR				Dupas tetraplex PCR			
	CTAB		DNeasy Plant Mini Kit		CTAB		QuickPick SML Plant DNA	
	L17		L18		L09		L09	
	TaqMan Fast Universal Master Mix (AB)	PerfeCTa qPCR ToughMix (Quantabio)	TaqMan Fast Universal Master Mix (AB)	PerfeCTa qPCR ToughMix (Quantabio)	Brilliant Multiplex qPCR Master Mix (Agilent)	SsoAdvanced Universal Probes Supermix (Bio-Rad)	Brilliant Multiplex qPCR Master Mix (Agilent)	SsoAdvanced Universal Probes Supermix (Bio-Rad)
Sensitivity	100	85,7 ^a	100	100	100	71,4 ^b	100	100
Specificity	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Accuracy	100	88,9 ^a	100	100	100	77,8 ^b	100	100

^a Lack of sensitivity on sample H

^b Lack of sensitivity on samples E and I

X. fastidiosa detection:

- Using the PerfeCTa qPCR ToughMix, a lack of sensitivity was observed by L17 on one sample (H) to detect *X. fastidiosa* (CTAB/Harper simplex), although it was used to reliably detect *X. fastidiosa* by L18 (DNeasy/Harper simplex).
- The TaqMan Fast Universal Mastermix was used to reliably detect *X. fastidiosa* by both laboratories.

Subspecies determination:

- Using the SsoAdvanced Universal Probes Supermix, a lack of sensitivity was observed on two samples (E and I) to determine subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* (CTAB/Dupas tetraplex), although it was used to reliably determine subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* with another DNA extraction protocol (QuickPick/Dupas tetraplex).
- The Brilliant Multiplex qPCR Master Mix was used to reliably determine subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* (CTAB/Dupas tetraplex and QuickPick/Dupas tetraplex).

Repeatability

Repeatability was calculated for protocols that have been tested by at least three laboratories: Harper simplex (CTAB/DNeasy/Quickpick), Hodgetts simplex (CTAB/Quickpick) and Dupas tetraplex (Quickpick) (Table 21). The repeatability of the different methods was very good.

Table 21. Repeatability using the results obtained for Harper simplex, Hodgetts simplex and Dupas tetraplex PCR methods

Laboratory code	Harper simplex			Hodgetts simplex		Dupas tetraplex ^f
	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
L01	90,3	100				
L02 ^b	100		100			100
L03	94,4			100		
L04 ^a		100	100			
L05	100	87,5				
L08 ^a	100	100		100		
L09	100		91,7	100	100 d	90,3
L10	95,8		100	100	100	
L11			100			
L13	100		100			100
L15 ^a	95,8					
L16			100		100	
L17	94,4					
L18		100				
All laboratories	97,1	97,5	98,8	100	100	96,8
N	10	5	7	4	3	3

^a no sonication

^b this laboratory used TaqMan™ Environmental Master Mix 2.0 (AB)

^d no Hodgetts simplex for Xfm

^f Dupas tetraplex: different sets used

Reproducibility

Reproducibility was calculated for methods that have been tested by at least three laboratories: Harper simplex (CTAB/DNeasy/Quickpick), Hodgetts simplex (CTAB/Quickpick) and Dupas tetraplex (Quickpick) (Table 22). The reproducibility of the different methods was very good.

Table 22. Reproducibility using the results obtained for Harper simplex, Hodgetts simplex and Dupas tetraplex PCR methods

	Harper simplex			Hodgetts simplex		Dupas tetraplex
	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
All laboratories	97,8	89,3*	97,3	95,8	95,1	100
N	10	5	7	4	3	3

* 100% if exclusion of L05 which is not experienced in this extraction method

5.2.2 Quantitative results

The Cq values obtained for the real-time PCR Harper simplex were compared with different methods of extraction (CTAB/DNeasy Plant Mini Kit/Quickpick SML Plant DNA) (Table 23, Figure 6).

Table 23. Cq values comparison for the real-time PCR Harper simplex following different methods of DNA extraction (CTAB/DNeasy Plant Mini Kit/Quickpick SML Plant DNA).

Samples	CTAB ^a		DNeasy ^b		QuickPick ^c	
	average	SD	average	SD	average	SD
B	25,32	3,85	26,95	5,43	27,39	0,89
C	27,07	3,38	29,79	5,99	29,07	1,03
D	28,64	3,92	30,30	6,40	29,70	2,01
E	28,54	3,50	32,32	3,84	31,00	1,67
F	28,15	2,76	30,72	5,00	29,69	1,00
H	30,88	3,22	31,17	3,24	31,56	1,32
I	28,19	3,34	30,58	4,13	29,34	2,03

^a 10 laboratories

^b 5 laboratories

^c 7 laboratories

Figure 6. Cq values comparison for the real time PCR Harper simplex following different methods of DNA extraction (CTAB/DNeasy Plant Mini Kit/Quickpick SML Plant DNA).

In Table 23 or Figure 6, no significant differences in Cq values were observed using the real time PCR Harper simplex, regardless of the extraction method used.

Detection of *X. fastidiosa* was validated in all infected samples using digital PCR (Table 24). Quantification varied according to laboratories.

Table 24. Digital PCR results (mean copies/mL of macerate)

Samples	L02		L13	L15
	CTAB	QuickPick	CTAB	Maxwell
A	42,2	/	/	/
B	3,6E+06	9,8E+05	9,7E+05	2,3E+07
C	1,9E+06	4,6E+05	1,3E+05	4,5E+06
D	1,5E+06	8,6E+05	3,8E+05	4,4E+06
E	4,9E+05	1,3E+05	1,2E+05	3,1E+06
F	4,4E+05	1,2E+05	3,4E+05	3,7E+06
G	/	/	/	/
H	1,2E+05	1,1E+05	1,0E+05	8,8E+05
I	5,0E+05	9,8E+04	1,4E+05	1,8E+06

6. SUMMARY OF THE OVERALL VALUES OBTAINED FOR EACH OF THE PERFORMANCE CRITERIA

Table 25 summarizes the values obtained for the performance criteria for selected methods (tested by more than three laboratories) tested in this TPS.

Table 25. Performance criteria values obtained for *X. fastidiosa* detection protocols, subspecies and ST determination protocols

Performance criteria	Harper simplex			Hodgetts simplex (Xfm)	Hodgetts simplex (Xff)		Hodgetts simplex (Xfp)		Dupas tetraplex
	CTAB	DNeasy Plant Mini Kit	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	CTAB	QuickPick SML Plant DNA	QuickPick SML Plant DNA
Diagnostic sensitivity	98,6	91,4	98,0	100	87,5	83,3	100	100	100
Diagnostic specificity	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Accuracy	98,9	93,3	98,4	100	97,2	94,4	100	100	100
Repeatability	97,1	97,5	98,8	100	100	100	100	100	96,8
Reproducibility	97,8	89,3	97,3	95,8	95,8	95,1	95,8	95,1	100
Number of laboratories	10	5	7	4	4	3	4	3	3

7 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

In this TPS, the Harper simplex method (following CTAB, DNeasy and Quickpick DNA extractions) was validated to detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants after being tested by a large number of laboratories. Other methods might also be usable to reliably detect *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants but they were tested by only one or two laboratories, so were not validated.

The Hodgetts simplex method (following CTAB DNA extraction for Xfm and following CTAB and Quickpick DNA extraction for Xff and Xfp) and the Dupas tetraplex method (following Quickpick DNA extraction) were validated to determine subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants after being tested by more than three laboratories. Other protocols are possibly also usable to reliably determine the subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* or ST in dormant plants but they were tested by only one or two laboratories, so were not validated.

The results of this collaborative work led to common standards for the detection of *X. fastidiosa* in dormant plants; these standards will be proposed for the next versions of the EPPO PM7/24 and ICPP DP25 diagnostic protocols for *X. fastidiosa*.

This TPS provides some remarks/recommendations for laboratories:

- Differences in laboratory experience with the extraction method may affect results.
- Tetraplex Dupas PCR can be used with an Applied Biosystems thermocycler, if the ROX is not used as a fluorophore.
- In this TPS, result was considered as negative in case of doubtful results (3 negative repeats and 1 positive) which could be due to cross contamination. In routine analysis, laboratory should retest the sample (repeat the PCR reaction) and in some cases repeat the DNA extraction; in case of same results at the retest, final result is negative; in case of positive result at the retest, the final result is positive.
- Taq polymerase can have various performances depending on the laboratory.
- Some laboratories didn't follow the recommendations given in the protocols which may affect their performance criteria.

8. REFERENCES

- Chabirand A, Anthoine G, Pierson O, Hostachy B (2014) The organization of proficiency testing in plant pathology (qualitative methods of analysis) according to the ISO/IEC 17043: example of the French national reference laboratory. *Accred Qual Assur*, 19, 111-125 DOI 10.1007/s00769-014-1034-y.
- Dupas E, Legendre B, Olivier V, Poliakoff F, Manceau C, Cuntz A (2019a) Comparison of real-time PCR and droplet digital PCR for the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* in plants. *Journal Microbiological Methods*, 162, 86-95. doi: 10.1016/j.mimet.2019.05.010. Epub 2019 May 22. PMID: 31125573.
- Dupas E, Briand M, Jacques MA, Cesbron S (2019b) Novel tetraplex quantitative PCR assays for simultaneous detection and identification of *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies in plant tissues. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10, 1732.
- Harper SJ, Ward LI, Clover GRG (2010) Development of LAMP and real-time PCR methods for the rapid detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* for quarantine and field applications. *Phytopathology*, 100, 1282-1288.
- Hodgetts J, Glover R, Cole J, Hall J, Boonham N. (2021) Genomics informed design of a suite of real-time PCR assays for the specific detection of each *Xylella fastidiosa* subspecies. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 131, 855-872. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.14903>
- Ios R, Fourrier C, Iancu G, Gordon TR (2009) Sensitive Detection of *Fusarium circinatum* in Pine Seed by Combining an Enrichment Procedure with a Real-Time Polymerase Chain Reaction Using Dual-Labeled Probe Chemistry. *Phytopathology*, 99, 5-0582
- PM 7/24 (5) (2023), *Xylella fastidiosa*. *EPPO Bulletin*, 53: 205–276. <https://doi.org/10.1111/epp.12923>.

9. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Bruno Legendre and Ugo Mouïsse (Anses, Laboratoire de la santé des végétaux, Angers, France) for help in preparing the TPS

Ester Marco Noales (Centro de Proteccion y Biotecnologia, Instituto de Investigaciones Agrarias, Valencia, Spain) for providing plant materials

Yael Meller Harel (Plant Protection and Inspection Services, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Israel) for providing plant materials

Maria Saponari (Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile, CNR, Bari, Italy) for providing plant materials

Annex I

Technical sheet: detailed protocols

Please see file attached.

Annex II

Participant contract

**Test performance study
for the detection of *Xylella fastidiosa*
in Mediterranean dormant plant species
Participant's contract**

To register for the Test Performance Study (TPS), please complete this form and return it by e-mail to: anne-laure.boutigny@anses.fr, Cc: ugo.mouisse.ext@anses.fr

Identification of the test performance study

Code: 23-XfDORM

Title: Test performance study of *Xylella fastidiosa* detection methods in dormant plant species

LABORATORY	
Name	
Delivery address	
Phone	
Institutional e-mail	

Registration

The laboratory agrees to participate in the TPS: Yes ⁽¹⁾ No

If no, indicate the reason(s) why (optional):

If yes, please provide all the information requested in the table below:

Communication	<p>1) Identify two contact persons for your laboratory :</p> <p>First name: First name:</p> <p>Last name: Last name:</p> <p>Function: Function:</p> <p>2) Provide two valid e-mail addresses (different persons) for the transmission of results and exchanges with the organizer :</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>
Analytical method	<p>3) Specify which method(s) you will apply:</p> <p>DNA extraction CTAB (EPPO PM7/24 (4)) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>DNA extraction QuickPick™ (Bio-Nobile) (EPPO PM7/24 (4)) Automate <input type="checkbox"/> or Manual <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>DNA extraction DNeasy Plant Mini Kit (Qiagen) (EPPO PM7/24 (4)) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other DNA extraction method <input type="checkbox"/> Specify which one:</p> <p>Real-time PCR Harper <i>et al.</i> (2010) (EPPO PM7/24 (4)) Simplex <input type="checkbox"/> or Duplex <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other PCR for Xf detection <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:</p> <p>Digital PCR <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Tetraplex real-time PCR Dupas <i>et al.</i> (2019) (EPPO PM7/24 (4)) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Simplex real-time PCR Dupas <i>et al.</i> (2019) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>MLST Yuan <i>et al.</i> (2010) (EPPO PM7/24 (4)) <input type="checkbox"/> Specify which gene:</p> <p>Real-time PCR Hodgetts <i>et al.</i> (2021) (EPPO PM7/24 (4)) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other PCR for subspecies determination <input type="checkbox"/> Specify:</p> <p><i>It should be noted that in order to evaluate one common protocol, it is recommended that each laboratory use the same DNA extraction and PCR technique, namely:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DNA extraction CTAB (EPPO PM7/24 (4)) • Real-time PCR Harper <i>et al.</i> (2010) (EPPO PM7/24 (4)) <p>The material provided is not in limited quantity and participating laboratories are welcome to perform additional analyses such as testing other DNA extraction and/or PCR methods.</p>

Regulatory requirements	<p>5) Specify the requirements concerning the phytosanitary regulations of your country (territory) to allow the sending of the samples (it should be noted that the samples will contain naturally infected twigs; a LOA is therefore mandatory for EU countries):</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No requirements</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Requirements⁽²⁾: <input type="checkbox"/> the package must be accompanied by a LOA ⁽³⁾ for EU countries</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify:</p> <p>⁽²⁾ IMPORTANT, if requirements are specified and the organiser doesn't have the necessary documents before the date set for sending the samples, the legislation will not allow the sending of the sample package and the laboratory's participation will be compromised.</p> <p>⁽³⁾ Letter of Authority authorising the circulation of a regulated pest in the European Union.</p>

⁽⁴⁾ By validating its registration, the laboratory identified on the first page of the contract (further mentioned just as « participating laboratory ») agrees to participate in the test performance study organised by ANSES (further mentioned just as « organiser »), in the following conditions:

Conditions of participation

1) Material :

For the purpose of this test, the organiser will provide:

- 1 panel of naturally contaminated and not contaminated dormant twigs (*Prunus domestica*, *Prunus dulcis*, *Vitis vinifera*)
- maximum 10 samples in each panel
- 1 sample will contain 10 cuttings of about 2 cm
- protocols (in the technical sheet).

The participating laboratory will provide all reagents (primers, probes, enzymes and master mix). In the « result form », all the critical reagents (ex: master mix) and device (ex: thermocycler) will be listed by the participant.

2) Implementation of the test :

The participating laboratory agrees to perform analyses in its laboratory according to the instructions of the organiser (the enclosed technical sheet and the instruction sheet which will be sent together with the panel of samples), and in its usual conditions of work.

Any changes/deviation should be reported to the organiser. This type of information can be very important for the interpretation of the results.

The participating laboratory agrees to communicate any difficulties encountered during the implementation of the TPS.

The participating laboratory agrees to provide all results on the result form provided within the deadline indicated on the enclosed technical sheet.

3) Transmission of the results :

The report and the individual code of the participating laboratory will be transmitted, as specified in the technical sheet to each participating laboratory.

4) Confidentiality and collusion :

The organiser will provide each participating laboratory with a panel of coded samples. The different panels will be randomly assigned to the different participating laboratories. Coding of the samples will be kept confidential by the organiser until the end of the TPS.

Each participating laboratory agrees not to communicate with other participants or any third parties regarding the samples or any part of the results until the TPS report is submitted by the organiser.

Results obtained from the participants will be presented anonymously in order to ensure the confidentiality of their results towards other participants. Then each laboratory will be informed of its own code for the exploitation of results.

Participating laboratories are informed that the TPS results will be used anonymously for scientific purposes.

Participating laboratories are informed that they have the right to waive confidentiality within the TPS scheme for the purposes of discussion and mutual assistance or for scientific purposes.

Participating laboratories are informed that the TPS results could not be used for any commercial purposes.

5) Containment :

The participating laboratory must have adopted measures to prevent the risk of unintentional release of plant pathogens for which it is approved (containment, processing of waste, etc.).

The participating laboratory commits to inform the organiser in the participant's contract of the phytosanitary regulation requirements of its country (territory), in order to allow the sending of the naturally infected samples in conformity with its regulation. The participating laboratory also commits to complete the necessary formalities to allow the receipt of the samples and so to ensure its participation in the TPS.

Samples sent by the organiser must be used only in the framework of the TPS.

The ANSES declines any responsibility for the use of the samples or any remainder outside the implementation of the TPS.

Name of the laboratory manager :	Date :	Signature :

Annex III

Codification of samples by laboratory

Samples	Assigned value	Laboratory code													
		L01	L02	L03	L04	L05	L08	L09	L10	L11	L13	L15	L16	L17	L18
A	-	4	3	3	9	6	2	5	3	9	4	9	2	4	5
B	+	7	10	8	2	8	7	10	5	4	5	7	6	9	9
C	+	10	9	5	1	2	9	7	1	6	7	2	5	6	2
D	+	2	6	7	10	9	1	8	6	7	6	4	9	7	3
E	+	6	2	4	3	4	4	2	10	3	9	1	4	8	6
F	+	1	5	6	4	7	5	6	8	5	10	10	7	1	1
G	-	5	1	2	6	1	6	3	9	1	8	5	10	2	4
H	+	8	8	1	7	5	8	4	2	2	3	3	3	5	8
I	+	9	7	9	8	3	10	9	7	8	2	8	8	10	7
J	+ or -	3: A	4: B	10: C	5: A	10: B	3: B	1: D	4: E	10: B	1: D	6: E	1: F	3: B	10: B